

1 **Ontogeny of the circadian system: A multiscale process throughout development**

2 Maria Comas¹, Davide De Pietri Tonelli², Luca Berdondini³ and Mariana Astiz^{1,4,5*}

3

4 ¹Circadian Physiology of Neurons and Glia Laboratory, Achucarro Basque Center for
5 Neuroscience, 48940 Leioa, Basque Country, Spain.

6 ²Neurobiology of miRNA, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT), 16163 Genova, Italy.

7 ³Microtechnology for Neuroelectronics, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT), 16163
8 Genova, Italy.

9 ⁴IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, Spain.

10 ⁵Institute of Neurobiology, University of Lübeck, 23562 Lübeck, Germany.

11

12 *Correspondence: Mariana Astiz, PhD. Circadian Physiology of Neurons and Glia Laboratory,
13 Achucarro Basque Center for Neuroscience, 48940 Leioa, Basque Country, Spain. Email:
14 mariana.astiz@achucarro.org. Tel: +34 946018160

15 **Keywords:** circadian clock, mouse, humans, suprachiasmatic nuclei, astrocytes, neurons

16 **Abstract:**

17 The 24 h (circadian) timing system develops in mammals during the perinatal period. It carries
18 out the essential task of anticipating daily recurring environmental changes to identify the
19 best time of day for each molecular, cellular and systemic process. While significant knowledge
20 has been acquired about the organization and function of the adult circadian system, relatively
21 little is known about its ontogeny. During the perinatal period, the circadian system
22 progressively gains functionality under the influence of the early environment. This review
23 explores current evidence on the development of the circadian clock in mammals, highlighting
24 the multi-level complexity of the process and the importance of gaining better understanding
25 of its underlying biology.

26

27 ***The emergence of the mammalian circadian system***

28 Life on Earth has evolved under the influence of geophysical cycles that generate recurrent
29 environmental changes with stable periods. The **diurnal oscillations** (see glossary) of light
30 intensity and temperature, as a result of the Earth rotating around its axis, have a period of 24
31 hours (h) and influence every organism's physiology. These oscillations are efficiently
32 anticipated by the circadian system, which is necessary for organizing sleep-wake cycles and
33 most physiological rhythms to match the 24 h environmental period (the term circadian
34 derives from the Latin words *circa* – approximately, and *dies* – day) (reviewed in [1]). The
35 circadian system can be conceptualized as a three-component system: it requires **input**
36 pathways providing temporal information to an “entrainable” (but self-sustained) **oscillator**
37 which is, in turn, able to produce the rhythmic **output** necessary to synchronize different
38 processes. In multicellular organisms this three-component system can be found at **three**
39 **levels: molecular, tissue/circuit and systemic** [2].

40 Compared with the knowledge that has been acquired on the adult circadian system, its
41 ontogeny is not well understood. The mammalian circadian system gains functionality
42 progressively under the dynamic influence of the perinatal environment (reviewed in [3]). In
43 both rodents and humans, the perinatal period is considered the critical window when the
44 development and maturation of the system takes place. While in humans most hypothalamic
45 nuclei, including the master clock in the suprachiasmatic nuclei (SCN), are mature by the end
46 of gestation, in rodents this process continues after birth (reviewed in [4]).

47 With a brief introduction on how the circadian system is organized in adults, this review
48 focuses on current evidence on the ontogeny of the master clock in mammals at the
49 molecular, circuit and systemic level. We highlight some of the less explored aspects of this
50 complex process and discuss the need for better understanding the influence of an adverse
51 perinatal environment later in life.

52

53 ***How is the adult circadian system organized?***

54 Circadian rhythms in mammals are coordinated at **systemic level** by the master pacemaker in
55 the SCN, located on each side of the third ventricle (3V) and above the optic chiasm (OC). Light

56 signals are received by the retina and transmitted through neuronal pathways to the SCN,
57 thus, entraining the oscillator to the 24 h light-dark cycle [5,6]. In absence of light input, the
58 oscillator maintains self-sustained rhythms, with a period that approximates 24 h (τ) [7–9].
59 The ability of the SCN to synchronize rhythms systemically, relies on extensive neuronal
60 projections and paracrine communication. These pathways reach different brain areas
61 including the medial hypothalamus coordinating hormone release and the tone of the
62 autonomic nervous system [10]. Two well-known examples of hormonal outputs are the
63 secretions of melatonin (during the dark phase) and glucocorticoids (GCs, before the active
64 phase) [11–13]. The SCN has been identified as the master circadian pacemaker by lesion
65 experiments. SCN-lesioned rats showed arrhythmic behavior, evidenced by an altered pattern
66 of locomotor activity, disrupted sleep-wake and feeding-fasting cycles and loss of circadian
67 hormonal levels [7,14]. The systemic rhythmicity can be restored by transplanting a graft
68 containing SCN in the lesion site, even if the graft is wrapped in a mesh blocking efferent
69 outgrowth, evidencing the relevance of paracrine output signals [15,16]. These key
70 discoveries, were followed by the characterization of neuronal populations, coupling
71 mechanisms between neighboring cells within the circuit, and the synaptic and paracrine
72 signalling pathways that keep the time.

73 The master clock **circuit** in adult rodents is formed by few thousands GABAergic neurons
74 highly interconnected, exhibiting precise and high amplitude circadian cycles of gene
75 expression, metabolic and electrical activity that persist autonomously in absence of light and
76 when cultured *in vitro* [17]. Topologically, the SCN is divided into a ventral core and a dorsal
77 shell. Neurons from the core receive glutamatergic innervation from the retina and propagate
78 their activation to the surrounding shell by releasing mainly gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)
79 and vasoactive intestinal polypeptide (Vip). Shell neurons, which in absence of light show
80 autonomous time-keeper activity with a period \sim 24 h, are then entrained and transfer their
81 synchrony to downstream clocks through efferent connections releasing vasopressin (Avp),
82 GABA and other signals (reviewed in [18]). Paracrine communication within the SCN circuit is
83 mediated by an heterogenous array of hundreds of neuropeptides (e.g. gastrin-releasing
84 peptide (Grp), neuromedin-S (Nms), among others) which are believed to confer the network-
85 level properties necessary to maintain highly robust oscillations even in absence of
86 environmental input [19]. This traditional neuron-centric view of the circuit has changed over

87 time, with demonstrations in rodents that astrocytes are competent circadian oscillators,
88 being able to modulate the clockwork of other cell types ([20–22], reviewed in [23]). In mice,
89 the astrocytes' clock is sufficient and partially necessary to drive neuronal **circadian rhythms**
90 in the SCN, very likely contributing to the highly robust oscillations of the circuit [24–28]. In
91 light of this evidence, the current view on the adult SCN assumes a tight neuron-astrocyte
92 interaction, modulating paracrine and synaptic communication to maintain the circuit-level
93 properties of the oscillator and long-range organization of the output within and outside the
94 SCN (reviewed in [29]). As in the SCN, most other tissues/circuits show coupled oscillations
95 between neighboring cells, although they tend to lose synchrony in absence of timing cues.
96 The weaker coupling of extra-SCN tissues and the input-dependent synchrony seems to be
97 essential for the top-to-bottom coordination of tissue-specific circadian functions (reviewed
98 in [30]).

99 The **molecular clock**, which is present in virtually all the cells, is the third level of organization
100 of the circadian system. A set of core clock proteins (e.g., BMAL1, CLOCK, PER1-3, CRY1-2,
101 ROR α , REV-ERB α/β) generate self-sustained oscillations that can be entrained by input signals.
102 As a result, interlocked auto-regulatory transcription-translation feedback loops (TTFLs)
103 produce molecular rhythms of about 24 h (reviewed in [31]). The TTFL regulates the rhythmic
104 expression of the so called “clock-controlled genes” (CCG) which represent, depending on the
105 cell type, between 10-40% of the transcriptome (reviewed in [32]). In addition, post-
106 transcriptional, translational and post-translational processes (including splicing,
107 polyadenylation, RNA binding proteins, **microRNAs** and other **epigenetic** and
108 **epitranscriptomic** mechanisms) were found to play a role in shaping the rhythmicity of
109 mRNAs, and in the accumulation of clock proteins [33–35]. The current knowledge on these
110 mechanisms is more limited.

111

112 ***What defines a functional circadian clock?***

113 The mature circadian system depends on its multilevel nature (i.e.: molecular, cellular and
114 systemic) and on the integration of the three components: input, oscillator and output (**Figure**
115 **1**). During development, the mammalian clock starts gaining function *in utero* and it matures
116 completely after birth (reviewed in [36–40]). Understanding this process in its complexity is

117 imperative, especially because during the last decade, studies have revealed an association
118 between **circadian disruption** during pregnancy/early postnatal life and poor
119 neurodevelopmental outcomes in animal models and humans ([41-46], reviewed in [47]). To
120 understand the ontogeny of the circadian system, two critical notions to consider are: that the
121 functional clock is defined as “**entrainable**” and as able to maintain **self-sustained rhythms**.
122 This implies that the temporal input pathways have to respond to time cues and synchronize
123 or “entrain” the oscillator with a 24 h period (T). Furthermore, in the absence of
124 environmental cues, the oscillator must have the ability to generate self-sustained rhythms
125 that approximate a 24 h period (τ). Lastly, the multiple output pathways must produce signals
126 with a stable phase relationship, or phase angle, between the input and the oscillator to
127 ensure proper systemic synchronization.

128 Circadian rhythms are therefore innate. What remains unclear is when, during the process of
129 ontogeny, the circadian system starts to tick in an integrated and multiscale manner and what
130 is the influence of the early environment shaping the gain of function. The main experimental
131 difficulty has been to dissect whether an oscillation is driven by an entrainment synchronizing
132 signal (e.g. maternal rhythmic hormones reaching fetal/newborn tissues) or whether it is self-
133 sustained and autonomously generated (e.g. by the fetal/newborn clock). Moreover, little is
134 known about how the maturation process is coordinated during the perinatal period and how
135 milestone/sequential events lead to the gradual gain of functionality. Current evidence in
136 rodents and humans shows that the environment to which the system is exposed to during
137 development is critical for defining its functionality later on. Thereby, the functional
138 maturation of the circadian system results from a complex and likely dynamic interaction
139 between exogenous (i.e.: maternal/early environment signals) and endogenous factors (i.e.:
140 intrinsic molecular programs) (reviewed in [38], [47]). In the following sections we explore the
141 current knowledge on the maturation of the circadian system at all three levels, and discuss
142 current knowledge gaps.

143

144 ***The maturation of the molecular clock***

145 During mammalian embryonic development progenitor cells undergo precise fate decisions
146 to become functionally mature. Circadian oscillations in the expression of the clockwork genes

147 appear to be absent in pluripotent stem cells (either embryonic or induced) [48]. Rhythmic
148 clock gene expression arises progressively and gains amplitude as the cell fate becomes more
149 defined, suggesting a tight coupling between the development of a functional molecular clock
150 and the cellular differentiation states ([49], reviewed in [50]). Post-transcriptional suppression
151 of CLOCK protein has been identified as one of the mechanisms setting the time for the
152 molecular clock to start ticking [51]. However, cell differentiation depends on genetic and
153 epigenetic determinants modulating whole regulatory networks that specifically define the
154 fate of each cell. Therefore, it seems plausible that multiple gene-modulatory mechanisms
155 (posttranscriptional [52,53], translational [54] and posttranslational [34,35,55] that are just
156 starting to be explored, play a role in this complex developmental process (reviewed in [56]).
157 As an example of the intricacy of these mechanisms, we highlight a link between **genomic**
158 **imprinting**, microRNAs, and light-experience during the critical period of the visual system
159 development in mice [57]. Interestingly, the majority of the imprinted miRNAs found, several
160 of which are known to control neural stem cell fate [58,59], were predominantly clustered into
161 the Dlk1-Dio3 locus, a genomic region that is associated with neuronal plasticity and several
162 neurodevelopmental disorders (reviewed in [60]). Hence, post-transcriptional/translational
163 mechanisms in the context of circadian ontogeny are of interest for future investigations. In
164 mammals, however, these mechanisms were mostly studied in peripheral organs, such as liver
165 and intestine [61], and the contribution of these mechanisms in different regions of the brain,
166 or in neural cell subpopulations, remains largely unknown.

167 In the mouse embryo, the rhythmic expression of clock genes has been detected quite early,
168 at about two-thirds of the *in-utero* development (13 days of gestation) [62–65]. In the
169 hypothalamus, this developmental stage is comparable to the end of the third trimester in
170 humans [4]. However, it is possible that these rhythms are not self-sustained and only induced
171 by maternal entrainment signals *in vivo* or by the culture conditions *in vitro*. Several maternal
172 signals such as melatonin [66], dopamine [67,68] and glucocorticoids [41,69] are essential for
173 promoting fetal growth and tissue maturation as well as for communicating time. All three are
174 produced in a circadian manner and are able to cross the placenta and reach fetal tissues ([70],
175 reviewed in [38,71]). Interestingly, maternal SCN lesions in rats or experiments in mice done
176 with clock deficient dams (*Per1/Per2* double knockouts) have shown that during pregnancy,
177 the absence of maternal clock reduces the synchrony of fetal rhythms likely due to low

178 entrainment by maternal rhythmic signals [72,73]. However, the development of circadian
179 rhythms in pups is not impaired, suggesting a certain degree of fetal/newborn clock autonomy
180 during development [74]. Indeed, it has been demonstrated in mice that the molecular clock
181 in the fetus, already at 15 days of gestation, is able to gate the sensitivity of the fetal
182 hypothalamus to maternal glucocorticoids (GCs) at different times of day [41]. The modulation
183 observed in the activity of the GCs receptor in a circadian manner could be also relevant for
184 other maternal signals such as dopamine or melatonin [67,68,75]. These data suggest that
185 autonomic molecular clock mechanisms have an early role during fetal development, shaping
186 the influence of exogenous rhythmic signals. Similar mechanisms, that still need to be
187 explored, could be responsible for driving self-sustained molecular oscillations (i.e.:
188 functionality) of the developing clock.

189

190 ***The intercellular/circuit level maturation of the clock***

191 Due to its complex structure, highly diverse cell composition and anatomical location, the
192 study of hypothalamic development has been slower than for other brain regions (reviewed
193 in [76]). The maturation of the SCN as a circuit result from a dynamic interplay between time
194 cues produced by the mother and intrinsic molecular programs, with variable influence along
195 the perinatal developmental window. During this period, the SCN circuit progresses from a
196 collection of undifferentiated individual cells to a highly differentiated, interconnected and
197 synchronised multicellular network. In mice, around the time of neurogenesis (between
198 gestational day (GD) 10-15), SCN cells express low amplitude clock genes oscillations with low
199 intercellular synchrony [77]. By the time when the afferent retinal projections reach the SCN
200 and the eyes open (around postnatal day (PND) 12) [78,79], the circuit shows high amplitude
201 clock gene oscillations and high intercellular synchrony (**Figure 2**). In mice and other rodents,
202 neurons of the core and the shell of the SCN seem to have different ontogeny timing [80].
203 Cells born around GD12 are mainly confined to the core, whereas cells produced later, around
204 GD 13-14, form the shell and distribute to the posterior and anterior areas of the SCN [80]. To
205 the best of our knowledge, no functional link of this differential ontogenic timing has been
206 described so far. The importance of paracrine signaling promoting the network level
207 properties of the SCN circuit was demonstrated in foundational studies showing that in SCN-
208 lesioned rodents the systemic rhythmicity can be restored by transplanting a graft containing

209 SCN [16], even if the graft is wrapped in a mesh blocking efferent outgrowth [15]. Interestingly,
210 the capacity of the graft to rescue the rhythmicity strongly depends on the age of the donor
211 (grafts of hamster pups older than PND7 lose the ability to rescue circadian rhythmicity) [81].
212 Furthermore, experiments done with organotypic cultures have shown that the way in which
213 rhythms are coordinated changes along development depending on Vip and Avp signaling, but
214 independently of the presence of key members of the molecular clock machinery [82,83]. This
215 was demonstrated by culturing neonatal SCN tissue slices obtained from both wild-type and
216 Cry1/2 double knockout mice, showing the ability of both to entrain rhythmicity in an
217 arrhythmic adult SCN from Cry1/2 double knockout [82]. Overall, these data suggest that the
218 contribution of paracrine and synaptic signaling might change along SCN development.

219 Moreover, GABA-ergic circuits, such as the SCN, might be impacted by the GABA excitatory-
220 inhibitory switch, as the circuit matures. In rodents, the switch relies on changes in the
221 chloride (Cl⁻) flow dependent on the activation of Cl⁻-permeable GABA_A receptors [84]. During
222 development, the Na-K-2Cl cotransporter isoform 1 (NKCC1, promoting Cl⁻ accumulation)
223 downregulates, while the K-Cl cotransporter isoform 2 (KCC2, promoting Cl⁻ extrusion)
224 upregulates, thus, switching from an excitatory to an inhibitory circuit [84]. Perturbations in
225 the timing when this switch takes place have been proposed as a potential cause of circuit
226 malfunction in the context of conditions such as Down syndrome [85,86], epilepsy [87], autism
227 [88], Rett syndrome [89–91], fragile X syndrome [92,93], 22q11.2 microdeletion syndrome
228 [94], schizophrenia [95], Huntington's disease [96,97] and behavioral disorders associated
229 with an early adverse environment [98,99]. However, to our knowledge, this possibility has
230 not been explored in the context of SCN development. In the adult mouse SCN, the GABAergic
231 excitation/inhibition ratio (E/I ratio) increases in SCN neurons exposed to long day
232 photoperiod compared to short day photoperiod, indicating that a certain degree of plasticity
233 remains even when the circuit is fully mature [100,101].

234 Furthermore, the fact that the function of the adult circadian circuit in the mouse depends on
235 neuron-astrocyte interaction suggests that the ontology might be influenced by (or involve)
236 proliferation and functional maturation of astrocytes. Astrocytes are organized in structurally
237 non-overlapping domains [102], being able to integrate information at multiple scales within
238 a neuronal circuit [103] and even to respond to signals derived from the environment
239 (reviewed in [104]). Gap junctions-mediated communication ([24,105,106], reviewed in

240 [107]), glutamate release [25] and GABA uptake [28,108] have been found to be essential for
241 the time-keeping role of astrocytes in the adult SCN. Astrocytes can actively support long-
242 range molecular clock synchronization of segregated neuronal populations, for which gap
243 junctions-mediated communication is required [103]. Moreover, the local proliferation and
244 expansion of astrocytes occurring during perinatal development is regarded as the major
245 developmental origin of astrocytes in the mammalian cerebral cortex and might happen also
246 in the hypothalamus [109,110]. The current view is that astrocytes are modulators of neuronal
247 communication and close partners of neurons for regulating complex circuit level functions
248 and behavior such as sleep ([111,112], reviewed by [113]). Therefore, it is likely that astrocytes
249 are as heterogeneous as neurons in phenotype and function ([114], reviewed in [115]). Since
250 astrocytes and the circadian system develop simultaneously during the perinatal period in
251 mice, it is possible that astrocytes contribute at various levels to the gain of robustness of the
252 circadian circuit [116,117]. Indeed, mathematical models suggest a positive correlation
253 between the density of astrocyte-neuron connectivity and the coordination and amplitude of
254 rhythms [118]. Much work remains to be done in order to understand the interrelationships
255 between the co-occurring events of SCN cell ontogeny, the variable contribution of paracrine
256 signals, the GABA switch, and the proliferation of astrocytes.

257

258 ***The maturation of SCN neuronal afferent and efferent connections***

259 The integration of time-giving signals and the coordination of circadian rhythms at the
260 systemic level, requires the afferent connections to the SCN and efferent connections from it
261 to become mature. In mice, the maturation of the neuronal connection between the retina
262 and the SCN through the retino-hypothalamic tract (RHT), might be one of the main
263 milestones of the master clock's development. The melanopsin containing intrinsic
264 photosensitive retinal ganglion cells (ipRGCs) convey photic input to the SCN. Interestingly, in
265 mice, these neurons are born and mature throughout a much wider window than SCN
266 neurons, i.e., during GDs 11-18. IpRGCs are glutamatergic neurons that are already able to
267 activate SCN neurons by PNDs 0-1, and complete their innervation around PND7 ([78, 79],
268 reviewed in [39]). These events, are taking place before eyes open (which happens at about
269 PND12 in the mouse) [79]. Interestingly, it has been suggested that the postnatal development
270 of SCN astrocytes might be promoted by the RHT innervation [116]. Indeed, in hamsters,

271 bilateral enucleation at birth reduces the number of GFAP positive cells in the SCN and further
272 abolishes the diurnal variation of astrocytic coverage observed in adults [117] (**Figure 2**). The
273 mammalian retina itself has an autonomous (extra-SCN) clock that can be entrained by light
274 and in which also retinal glial oscillators appear to play a role [119– 122]. Interestingly, in the
275 mouse immature retina, the neuronal clock and the light environment regulate angiogenesis,
276 revealing that the embryonic retina requires these inputs to establish a robust light driven
277 circadian oscillator [123]. Therefore, light plays a critical role in the regulation of the
278 development of both the retina, the retinal clock and the SCN, suggesting an interrelated, yet
279 unclear, series of events that need to happen to acquire the features of an entrainable
280 oscillator.

281 Other afferents apart from the retinal input reach the SCN as well. These include afferents
282 from the intergeniculate leaflet (IGL) and the median raphe nucleus, which provide non-photoc
283 input, using neuropeptide Y (NPY) and serotonin as transmitters, respectively. In rodents,
284 these afferents mature at around the same time than the RHT and evidence suggests that the
285 maturation of the pathways is interdependent and that glial cells might be also involved [124–
286 126]. Furthermore, evidence from mouse experiments show that perinatal exposure to
287 agonists of these neurotransmitters has a negative impact on the maturation of afferents,
288 affecting the SCN response to photic and non-photoc temporal cues [127].

289 The SCN has direct and indirect connections with other brain regions, mainly subregions of
290 the hypothalamus and thalamus. The rodents SCN is intricately connected with the
291 paraventricular nuclei of the hypothalamus (PVN), controlling the timing of hormonal
292 secretion and the tone of the autonomic nervous system [10,128]. Direct efferent SCN
293 projections reach other hypothalamic nuclei such as arcuate nucleus [129] and dorsomedial
294 nucleus [130], while indirectly other hypothalamic and extrahypothalamic nuclei [131–133].
295 SCN efferents also reach the pineal gland, triggering the production of melatonin [133].
296 Furthermore, Avp+ efferents and a venous vascular system connects the SCN with neurons in
297 the nearby circumventricular organ, particularly the *organum vasculosum* of the lamina
298 terminalis (OVLT), mediating the release and transport of diffusible signals [134, 135]. Little is
299 known about the developmental windows in which SCN efferents mature, representing
300 another area of research that would need further investigation.

301

302 ***Translational value of learning when and how does the clock start to tick***

303 In humans, the exposure to a 24 h cycle in which the transition between day (light) and night
304 (dark) is frequently misaligned with the endogenous rhythms, reduces the ability of the
305 circadian system to anticipate changes. Such “circadian disruptive” environment is favored by
306 a lifestyle in which people are exposed to artificial light during the dark, work in night-shifts,
307 travel across time zones or spend several dark hours in front of screens. Evidence from
308 epidemiological studies in humans and animal experiments, shows multiple negative effects
309 of being exposed to a disruptive circadian environment especially during pregnancy, not only
310 for the mother but also for the offspring [41–46,136–138]. Most of this evidence is
311 correlational and few molecular links have been identified to explain the long-term effects
312 caused by a circadian disruption during gestation [e.g.: 41]. To gain a better understanding of
313 the underlying mechanisms would require experimental approaches studying the complex
314 interplay between endogenous and exogenous factors and the temporal windows of influence
315 during the process (see outstanding questions). In this context, one can hypothesize that the
316 sooner the rhythms stabilize, the better the long-term physiological outcomes may be. An
317 early organization of the circadian rhythms could show beneficial health effects by stabilizing
318 sleep-wake cycles, metabolism and behavior.

319

320 ***Concluding remarks and future perspectives***

321 Circadian rhythms undergo a maturation process at multiple levels starting *in utero* and
322 continuing throughout the postnatal period, shaped by the early environment. There is no
323 clear consensus currently on what defines a fully functional circadian system during
324 development, an issue that becomes essential for further progress. A multidisciplinary
325 approach is necessary to gain deeper insight into critical temporal windows, critical
326 environmental factors and critical endogenous mechanisms. The combination of large-scale
327 studies of transcriptional/post-transcriptional/post-translational landscapes, imaging,
328 electrophysiology, lineage tracing experiments and mathematical modelling might be needed.
329 Studies along these lines would shed light on regulatory networks and milestone events
330 crucial for the gradual development of the circadian system.

331

332

333 **Glossary:**

334 **Circadian disruption:** Circadian disruption results from misalignment between external timing
335 cues and endogenously generated rhythms.

336 **Circadian rhythm:** A biological rhythm occurring with a period of approximately a day, that
337 persists in constant environmental conditions.

338 **Diurnal rhythm:** a rhythm occurring with a period of 24 h driven by external time cues.

339 **Entrainment:** The synchronization or alignment of the phase and period of the circadian
340 rhythms to external time cues.

341 **Epigenetic:** dynamic modifications that regulate gene expression without changing the DNA
342 sequence

343 **Epigenome:** refers to genome-wide state of the epigenetic status of a cell.

344 **Epitranscriptomic:** dynamic chemical modifications that occur on RNA molecules, also known
345 as RNA modifications. These modifications involve the various enzymes known as writers/
346 erasers, or modifiers that respectively control addition, removal, or alteration of specific
347 chemical groups to the RNA nucleotides.

348 **Genomic imprinting:** A process by which only one copy of a gene (either from the mother or
349 the father) is expressed, while the other copy is suppressed.

350 **Input:** In the context of circadian rhythms, 'input' refers to pathways that convey exogenous
351 or endogenous signal providing a timing cue for the clock.

352 **MicroRNA:** single-stranded noncoding RNAs of about 22 nucleotides in length, which bind by
353 imperfect complementarity to their targets (mostly mRNAs) and repress their translation
354 initiation and stability.

355 **Oscillator:** networks of biochemical feedback loops that generate 24 h rhythms at the
356 molecular, cellular and multicellular levels.

357 **Output:** In the context of circadian rhythms, 'output' refers to pathways that convey
358 endogenous generated signals providing a timing cue for downstream processes.

359 **Perinatal period:** The developmental period around birth

360 **Self-sustained rhythms:** Physiological rhythms that persist in constant environmental
361 conditions

362

363 **Acknowledgements:** This work was supported by the Spanish Research Grants PID2021-
364 122694OB-I00 funded by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovacion (MCIN), by Achucarro Basque
365 Center for Neuroscience and Basque Foundation of Science (Ikerbasque) to MA. DDPT and LB
366 were supported by intramural funding of the Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, and
367 partly by: “PNRR—CENTRO NAZIONALE 3—Sviluppo di terapia genica e farmaci con tecnologia
368 RNA” to DDPT.

369

370 **Declaration of Interests:** The authors declare no competing interests in relation to this work.

371

372 **References:**

373 1. Dibner, C. *et al.* (2010) The mammalian circadian timing system: organization and
374 coordination of central and peripheral clocks. *Annu. Rev. Physiol.* 72, 517–549

375 2. Olmo, M.D *et al.* (2022) Mathematical Modeling in Circadian Rhythmicity. *Methods Mol.*
376 *Biol.* 2482, 55–80

377 3. Christ, E. *et al.* (2012) When does it start ticking? Ontogenetic development of the
378 mammalian circadian system. *Prog. Brain Res.* 199, 105–118

379 4. Benevento, M. *et al.* (2022) Ontogenetic rules for the molecular diversification of
380 hypothalamic neurons. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 23, 611–627

381 5. Hattar, S. *et al.* (2002) Melanopsin-containing retinal ganglion cells: architecture,
382 projections, and intrinsic photosensitivity. *Science* 295, 1065–1070

383 6. Berson, D.M. *et al.* (2002) Phototransduction by retinal ganglion cells that set the
384 circadian clock. *Science* 295, 1070–1073

385 7. Stephan, F.K. and Zucker, I. (1972) Circadian rhythms in drinking behavior and locomotor
386 activity of rats are eliminated by hypothalamic lesions. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 69,
387 1583–1586

388 8. Eckel-Mahan, K. and Sassone-Corsi, P. (2015) Phenotyping Circadian Rhythms in Mice.
389 *Curr. Protoc. Mouse Biol.* 5, 271–281

390 9. Goltsev, A.V. *et al.* (2022) Generation and Disruption of Circadian Rhythms in the
391 Suprachiasmatic Nucleus: A Core-Shell Model. *J. Biol. Rhythms* 37, 545–561

- 392 10. Buijs, R.M. *et al.* (2003) The suprachiasmatic nucleus balances sympathetic and
393 parasympathetic output to peripheral organs through separate preautonomic neurons. *J.*
394 *Comp. Neurol.* 464, 36–48
- 395 11. Klein, D.C. and Moore, R.Y. (1979) Pineal N-acetyltransferase and hydroxyindole-O-
396 methyltransferase: control by the retinohypothalamic tract and the suprachiasmatic
397 nucleus. *Brain Res.* 174, 245–262
- 398 12. Oster, H. *et al.* (2006) The circadian rhythm of glucocorticoids is regulated by a gating
399 mechanism residing in the adrenal cortical clock. *Cell Metab.* 4, 163–173
- 400 13. Son, G.H. *et al.* (2008) Adrenal peripheral clock controls the autonomous circadian
401 rhythm of glucocorticoid by causing rhythmic steroid production. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S.*
402 *A.* 105, 20970–20975
- 403 14. Moore, R.Y. and Eichler, V.B. (1972) Loss of a circadian adrenal corticosterone rhythm
404 following suprachiasmatic lesions in the rat. *Brain Res.* 42, 201–206
- 405 15. Silver, R. *et al.* (1996) A diffusible coupling signal from the transplanted suprachiasmatic
406 nucleus controlling circadian locomotor rhythms *Nature*, 382, 810–813
- 407 16. Lehman, M.N. *et al.* (1987) Circadian rhythmicity restored by neural transplant.
408 Immunocytochemical characterization of the graft and its integration with the host brain. *J.*
409 *Neurosci.* 7, 1626–1638
- 410 17. Van den Pol, A.N. *et al.* (1992) Calcium excitability and oscillations in suprachiasmatic
411 nucleus neurons and glia in vitro. *J. Neurosci.* 12, 2648–2664
- 412 18. Hastings, M.H. *et al.* (2018) Generation of circadian rhythms in the suprachiasmatic
413 nucleus. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 19, 453–469
- 414 19. Lee, J.E. *et al.* (2013) Quantitative peptidomics for discovery of circadian-related
415 peptides from the rat suprachiasmatic nucleus. *J. Proteome Res.* 12, 585–593
- 416 20. Prolo, L.M. *et al.* (2005) Circadian rhythm generation and entrainment in astrocytes. *J.*
417 *Neurosci.*, 25, 404–408
- 418 21. Moriya, T. *et al.* (2000) Involvement of glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) expressed in
419 astroglial cells in circadian rhythm under constant lighting conditions in mice. *J. Neurosci.*
420 *Res.* 60, 212–218
- 421 22. Prosser, R.A. *et al.* (1994) A possible glial role in the mammalian circadian clock. *Brain*
422 *Res.* 643, 296–301
- 423 23. Astiz, M. *et al.* (2022) Astrocytes as essential time-keepers of the central pacemaker
424 *Glia*, 70, 808–819
- 425 24. Brancaccio, M. *et al.* (2019) Cell-autonomous clock of astrocytes drives circadian
426 behavior in mammals *Science*, 363, 187–192
- 427 25. Brancaccio, M. *et al.* (2017) Astrocytes Control Circadian Timekeeping in the

- 428 Suprachiasmatic Nucleus via Glutamatergic Signaling. *Neuron*, 93, 1420-1435
- 429 26. Tso, C.F. *et al.* (2017) Astrocytes Regulate Daily Rhythms in the Suprachiasmatic Nucleus
430 and Behavior. *Curr. Biol.* 27, 1055–1061
- 431 27. Patton, A.P. *et al.* (2022) Astrocytes sustain circadian oscillation and bidirectionally
432 determine circadian period, but do not regulate circadian phase in the suprachiasmatic
433 nucleus. *J. Neurosci.* 42, 5522–5537
- 434 28. Barca-Mayo, O. *et al.* (2017) Astrocyte deletion of *Bmal1* alters daily locomotor activity
435 and cognitive functions via GABA signalling. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 14336
- 436 29. Hastings, M.H. *et al.* (2023) Circadian Rhythms and Astrocytes: The Good, the Bad, and
437 the Ugly. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.* 46, 123–143
- 438 30. Pilonis, V. *et al.* (2020) The Concept of Coupling in the Mammalian Circadian Clock
439 Network. *J. Mol. Biol.* 432, 3618–3638
- 440 31. Takahashi, J.S. *et al.* (2017) Transcriptional architecture of the mammalian circadian
441 clock. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 18, 164–179
- 442 32. Doherty, C.J. and Kay, S.A. (2010). Circadian control of global gene expression patterns.
443 *Annu. Rev. Genet.* 44, 419–444
- 444 33. Lee, C. *et al.* (2001) Posttranslational mechanisms regulate the mammalian circadian
445 clock. *Cell*, 107, 855–867
- 446 34. Brüning, F. *et al.* (2019) Sleep-wake cycles drive daily dynamics of synaptic
447 phosphorylation. *Science*, 366, 3617.
- 448 35. Noya, S.B. *et al.* (2019) The forebrain synaptic transcriptome is organized by clocks but
449 its proteome is driven by sleep. *Science*, 366, 2642
- 450 36. Wong, S.D. *et al.* (2022) Development of the circadian system in early life: maternal and
451 environmental factors. *J. Physiol. Anthropol.* 41, 22
- 452 37. Sumová, A. and Čechmanová, V. (2020) Mystery of rhythmic signal emergence within the
453 suprachiasmatic nuclei. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 51, 300–309
- 454 38. Astiz, M. and Oster, H. (2020) Feto-Maternal Crosstalk in the Development of the
455 Circadian Clock System. *Front. Neurosci.* 14, 631687
- 456 39. Bedont, J.L. and Blackshaw, S. (2015) Constructing the suprachiasmatic nucleus: a
457 watchmaker’s perspective on the central clockworks. *Front. Syst. Neurosci.* 9, 74
- 458 40. Landgraf, D. *et al.* (2014) Embryonic development of circadian clocks in the mammalian
459 suprachiasmatic nuclei. *Front. Neuroanat.* 8, 143
- 460 41. Astiz, M. *et al.* (2020) The circadian phase of antenatal glucocorticoid treatment affects
461 the risk of behavioral disorders. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 3593
- 462 42. Ameen, R.W. *et al.* (2022) Early life circadian rhythm disruption in mice alters brain and

463 behavior in adulthood. *Sci Rep*, 12, 7366

464 43. Salazar E.R. *et al.* (2018) Gestational chronodisruption leads to persistent changes in the
465 rat fetal and adult adrenal clock and function. *J. Physiol.* 596, 5839–5857

466 44. Smarr, B.L. *et al.* (2017) Maternal and Early-Life Circadian Disruption Have Long-Lasting
467 Negative Consequences on Offspring Development and Adult Behavior in Mice. *Sci. Rep.* 7,
468 3326

469 45. Varcoe, T.L. *et al.* (2016) The impact of prenatal circadian rhythm disruption on
470 pregnancy outcomes and long-term metabolic health of mice progeny. *Chronobiol. Int.* 33,
471 1171–1181

472 46. Jørgensen, J.T. *et al.* (2021) Shift work and incidence of psychiatric disorders: The Danish
473 Nurse Cohort study. *J. Psychiatr. Res.* 139, 132–138

474 47. Logan, R.W. and McClung, C.A. (2019) Rhythms of life: circadian disruption and brain
475 disorders across the lifespan. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 20, 49–65

476 48. Yagita, K. *et al.* (2010) Development of the circadian oscillator during differentiation of
477 mouse embryonic stem cells in vitro. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 107, 3846–3851

478 49. Dolatshad, H. *et al.* (2010) Differential expression of the circadian clock in maternal and
479 embryonic tissues of mice. *PLoS One* 5, 9855

480 50. Umemura, Y. and Yagita, K. *et al.* (2020) Development of the Circadian Core Machinery
481 in Mammals. *J. Mol. Biol.* 432, 3611–3617

482 51. Umemura, Y. *et al.* (2017) Involvement of posttranscriptional regulation of Clock in the
483 emergence of circadian clock oscillation during mouse development. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.*
484 *S. A.* 114, E7479–E7488

485 52. Fustin, J.M. *et al.* (2013) RNA-methylation-dependent RNA processing controls the speed
486 of the circadian clock. *Cell*, 155, 793–806

487 53. Kojima, S. *et al.* (2012) Circadian control of mRNA polyadenylation dynamics regulates
488 rhythmic protein expression. *Genes Dev.* 26, 2724–2736

489 54. Umemura, Y. *et al.* (2014) Transcriptional program of Kpna2/Importin- α 2 regulates
490 cellular differentiation-coupled circadian clock development in mammalian cells. *Proc. Natl.*
491 *Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 111, E5039-5048

492 55. Lee, H. *et al.* (2009) Essential roles of CKIdelta and CKIepsilon in the mammalian
493 circadian clock. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 106, 21359–21364

494 56. Anna, G. and Kannan, N.N. (2021) Post-transcriptional modulators and mediators of the
495 circadian clock. *Chronobiol. Int.* 38, 1244–1261

496 57. Hsu, C.L. *et al.* (2018) Analysis of experience-regulated transcriptome and imprintome
497 during critical periods of mouse visual system development reveals spatiotemporal
498 dynamics. *Hum. Mol. Genet.* 27, 1039–1054

- 499 58. Pons-Espinal, M. *et al.* (2017) Synergic Functions of miRNAs Determine Neuronal Fate of
500 Adult Neural Stem Cells. *Stem Cell Rep.* 8, 1046–1061
- 501 59. Pons-Espinal, M. *et al.* (2019) MiR-135a-5p Is Critical for Exercise-Induced Adult
502 Neurogenesis. *Stem Cell Rep.* 12, 1298–1312
- 503 60. Laufer, B.I. and Singh, S.M. (2012) A macro role for imprinted clusters of microRNAs in
504 the brain. *Microna* 1, 59–64
- 505 61. Freschi, A. *et al.* (2018) Tissue-specific and mosaic imprinting defects underlie opposite
506 congenital growth disorders in mice. *PLoS Genet.* 14, e1007243
- 507 62. Landgraf, D. *et al.* (2015) Embryonic development and maternal regulation of murine
508 circadian clock function. *Chronobiol. Int.* 32, 416–427
- 509 63. Čečmanová, V. *et al.* (2019) Development and Entrainment of the Fetal Clock in the
510 Suprachiasmatic Nuclei: The Role of Glucocorticoids. *J. Biol. Rhythms* 34, 307–322
- 511 64. Wreschnig, D. *et al.* (2014) Embryonic development of circadian oscillations in the
512 mouse hypothalamus. *J. Biol. Rhythms* 29, 299–310
- 513 65. Shimomura, H. *et al.* (2001) Differential daily expression of Per1 and Per2 mRNA in the
514 suprachiasmatic nucleus of fetal and early postnatal mice. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 13, 687–693
- 515 66. Davis, F.C. and Mannion, J. (1988) Entrainment of hamster pup circadian rhythms by
516 prenatal melatonin injections to the mother. *Am. J. Physiol.* 255, 439-448
- 517 67. Viswanathan, N. and Davis, F.C. (1997) Single prenatal injections of melatonin or the D1-
518 dopamine receptor agonist SKF 38393 to pregnant hamsters sets the offsprings' circadian
519 rhythms to phases 180 degrees apart. *J. Comp. Physiol. A* 180, 339–346
- 520 68. Viswanathan, N. *et al.* (1994) Entrainment of the fetal hamster circadian pacemaker by
521 prenatal injections of the dopamine agonist SKF 38393. *J. Neurosci.* 14, 5393–5398
- 522 69. Busada, J.T. and Cidlowski J.A. (2017) Mechanisms of Glucocorticoid Action During
523 Development. *Curr. Top Dev. Biol.* 125, 147–170
- 524 70. Lorelli, C. J. *et al.* (2011) Resilience of circadian pacemaker development in hamsters. *J.*
525 *Biol. Rhythms* 26, 221–229
- 526 71. Bates, K. and Herzog, E.D. (2020) Maternal-Fetal Circadian Communication During
527 Pregnancy. *Front. Endocrinol.* 11, 198
- 528 72. Reppert, S.M. and Schwartz, W. J. (1986) Maternal suprachiasmatic nuclei are necessary
529 for maternal coordination of the developing circadian system. *J. Neurosci.* 6, 2724–2729
- 530 73. Jud, C. and Albrecht, U. (2006) Circadian rhythms in murine pups develop in absence of a
531 functional maternal circadian clock. *J. Biol. Rhythms* 21, 149–154
- 532 74. Davis, F.C. and Gorski, R. A. (1988) Development of hamster circadian rhythms: role of
533 the maternal suprachiasmatic nucleus. *J. Comp. Physiol. A*, 162, 601–610

- 534 75. Mendez, N. *et al.* (2022) Maternal melatonin treatment rescues endocrine,
535 inflammatory, and transcriptional deregulation in the adult rat female offspring from
536 gestational chronodisruption. *Front. Neurosci.* 16, 1039977
- 537 76. Bedont, J.L. *et al.* (2015) Patterning, specification, and differentiation in the developing
538 hypothalamus. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Dev. Biol.* 4, 445–468
- 539 77. Carmona-Alcocer, V. *et al.* (2018) Ontogeny of Circadian Rhythms and Synchrony in the
540 Suprachiasmatic Nucleus. *J. Neurosci.* 38, 1326–1334
- 541 78. Sekaran, S. *et al.* (2005) Melanopsin-dependent photoreception provides earliest light
542 detection in the mammalian retina. *Curr. Biol.* 15, 1099–1107
- 543 79. Hoy, J. L. and Niell, C.M. (2015) Layer-specific refinement of visual cortex function after
544 eye opening in the awake mouse. *J. Neurosci.* 35, 3370–3383.
- 545 80. Kabrita, C.S. and Davis, F.C. (2008) Development of the mouse suprachiasmatic nucleus:
546 determination of time of cell origin and spatial arrangements within the nucleus. *Brain Res.*
547 1195, 20–27
- 548 81. Romero, M.T. *et al.* (1993) Age of donor influences ability of suprachiasmatic nucleus
549 grafts to restore circadian rhythmicity. *Brain Res. Dev. Brain Res.* 71, 45–52
- 550 82. Ono, D. *et al.* (2013) Cryptochromes are critical for the development of coherent
551 circadian rhythms in the mouse suprachiasmatic nucleus. *Nat. Commun.* 4, 1666
- 552 83. Ono, D. *et al.* (2016) Differential roles of AVP and VIP signaling in the postnatal changes
553 of neural networks for coherent circadian rhythms in the SCN. *Sci. Adv.* 2, e1600960
- 554 84. Ganguly, K. *et al.* (2001) GABA itself promotes the developmental switch of neuronal
555 GABAergic responses from excitation to inhibition. *Cell*, 105, 521–532
- 556 85. Deidda, G. *et al.* (2015) Reversing excitatory GABAAR signaling restores synaptic
557 plasticity and memory in a mouse model of Down syndrome. *Nat. Med.* 21, 318–326
- 558 86. Lysenko, L.V. *et al.* (2018) Developmental excitatory-to-inhibitory GABA polarity switch is
559 delayed in Ts65Dn mice, a genetic model of Down syndrome. *Neurobiol. Dis.* 115, 1–8
- 560 87. Kahle, K.T. *et al.* (2014) Genetically encoded impairment of neuronal KCC2 cotransporter
561 function in human idiopathic generalized epilepsy. *EMBO Rep.* 15, 766–774
- 562 88. Tyzio, R. *et al.* (2014) Oxytocin-mediated GABA inhibition during delivery attenuates
563 autism pathogenesis in rodent offspring. *Science* 343, 675–679
- 564 89. Lozovaya, N. *et al.* (2019) Early alterations in a mouse model of Rett syndrome: the
565 GABA developmental shift is abolished at birth. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 9276
- 566 90. Tang, X. *et al.* (2016) KCC2 rescues functional deficits in human neurons derived from
567 patients with Rett syndrome. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 113, 751–756
- 568 91. Banerjee, A. *et al.* (2016) Jointly reduced inhibition and excitation underlies circuit-wide
569 changes in cortical processing in Rett syndrome. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 113, E7287–

570 E7296

- 571 92. He, Q. *et al.* (2019) Critical period inhibition of NKCC1 rectifies synapse plasticity in the
572 somatosensory cortex and restores adult tactile response maps in fragile X mice. *mol.*
573 *Psychiatry* 24, 1732–1747
- 574 93. He, Q. *et al.* (2014) The developmental switch in GABA polarity is delayed in fragile X
575 mice. *J. Neurosci.* 34, 446–450
- 576 94. Amin, H. *et al.* (2017) Developmental excitatory-to-inhibitory GABA-polarity switch is
577 disrupted in 22q11.2 deletion syndrome: a potential target for clinical therapeutics. *Sci. Rep.*
578 7, 15752
- 579 95. Kim, H.R. *et al.* (2021). Depolarizing GABAA current in the prefrontal cortex is linked
580 with cognitive impairment in a mouse model relevant for schizophrenia. *Sci. Adv.* 7, 5032
- 581 96. Dargaei, Z. *et al.* (2018) Restoring GABAergic inhibition rescues memory deficits in a
582 Huntington's disease mouse model. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 115, E1618–E1626
- 583 97. Hsu, Y.T. *et al.* (2019) Enhanced Na⁺-K⁺-2Cl⁻ cotransporter 1 underlies motor
584 dysfunction in huntington's disease. *Mov. Disord.* 34, 845–857
- 585 98. Karst, H. *et al.* (2023). Acceleration of GABA-switch after early life stress changes mouse
586 prefrontal glutamatergic transmission. *Neuropharmacology* 234, 109543
- 587 99. Kang, E. *et al.* (2019) Interplay between a Mental Disorder Risk Gene and Developmental
588 Polarity Switch of GABA Action Leads to Excitation-Inhibition Imbalance. *Cell Rep.* 28, 1419-
589 1428
- 590 100. Farajnia, S. *et al.* (2014) Seasonal induction of GABAergic excitation in the central
591 mammalian clock. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 111, 9627–9632
- 592 101. Eick A. K. *et al.* (2022) The opposing chloride cotransporters KCC and NKCC control
593 locomotor activity in constant light and during long days. *Curr. Biol.* 32, 1420-1428
- 594 102. Ogata, K. and Kosaka, T. (2002) Structural and quantitative analysis of astrocytes in the
595 mouse hippocampus. *Neuroscience* 113, 221–233
- 596 103. Giantomasi, L. *et al.* (2023) Astrocytes actively support long-range molecular clock
597 synchronization of segregated neuronal populations. *Sci. Rep.* 13, 4815
- 598 104. Araque, A. *et al.* (2014) Gliotransmitters travel in time and space. *Neuron* 81, 728–739
- 599 105. Shinohara, K. *et al.* (2000). Effects of gap junction blocker on vasopressin and
600 vasoactive intestinal polypeptide rhythms in the rat suprachiasmatic nucleus in vitro.
601 *Neurosci. Res.* 38, 43–47
- 602 106. Clasadonte, J. *et al.* (2017) Connexin 43-Mediated Astroglial Metabolic Networks
603 Contribute to the Regulation of the Sleep-Wake Cycle. *Neuron*, 95, 1365-1380
- 604 107. Bennett, M.V.L. *et al.* (2003) New roles for astrocytes: gap junction hemichannels have
605 something to communicate. *Trends Neurosci.* 26, 610–617

606 108. Patton, A.P. *et al.* (2023) Astrocytic control of extracellular GABA drives circadian
607 timekeeping in the suprachiasmatic nucleus. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 120, e2301330120

608 109. Bandeira, F. *et al.* (2009) Changing numbers of neuronal and non-neuronal cells underlie
609 postnatal brain growth in the rat. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 106, 14108–14113

610 110. Ge, W.P. *et al.* (2012) Local generation of glia is a major astrocyte source in postnatal
611 cortex. *Nature* 484, 376–380

612 111. Bojarskaite, L. *et al.* (2020) Astrocytic Ca²⁺ signaling is reduced during sleep and is
613 involved in the regulation of slow wave sleep. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 3240

614 112. Ingiosi, A.M. *et al.* (2020) A Role for Astroglial Calcium in Mammalian Sleep and Sleep
615 Regulation. *Curr. Biol.* 30, 4373-4383.

616 113. Oliveira, J.F. *et al.* (2015). Do stars govern our actions? Astrocyte involvement in rodent
617 behavior. *Trends Neurosci.* 38, 535–549.

618 114. Götz, S. *et al.* (2021). Heterogeneity of astrocytes: Electrophysiological properties of
619 juxtavascular astrocytes before and after brain injury. *Glia* 69, 346–361

620 115. Ben Haim, L. and Rowitch, D.H. (2017) Functional diversity of astrocytes in neural
621 circuit regulation. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 18, 31–41

622 116. Munekawa, K. *et al.* (2000) Development of astroglial elements in the suprachiasmatic
623 nucleus of the rat: with special reference to the involvement of the optic nerve. *Exp. Neurol.*
624 166, 44–51

625 117. Lavialle, M. *et al.* (2001) Modifications of retinal afferent activity induce changes in
626 astroglial plasticity in the hamster circadian clock. *Glia* 34, 88–100

627 118. Sueviriyapan, N. *et al.* (2020) Astrocytic Modulation of Neuronal Activity in the
628 Suprachiasmatic Nucleus: Insights from Mathematical Modeling. *J. Biol. Rhythms*, 35, 287–
629 301

630 119. Tosini, G. and Menaker, M. (1996) Circadian rhythms in cultured mammalian retina.
631 *Science* 272, 419–421 10.1126/science.272.5260.419.

632 120. Ruan, G.X. *et al.* (2006). Circadian organization of the mammalian retina. *Proc. Natl.*
633 *Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 103, 9703–9708

634 121. Sakamoto, K. *et al.* (2000). Two circadian oscillatory mechanisms in the mammalian
635 retina. *Neuroreport.* 11, 3995–3997

636 122. Riccitelli, S. *et al.* (2022) Glial Bmal1 role in mammalian retina daily changes. *Sci. Rep.*
637 12, 21561

638 123. Jidigam, V.K. *et al.* (2022) Neuronal Bmal1 regulates retinal angiogenesis and
639 neovascularization in mice. *Commun. Biol.* 5, 792

640 124. Ferguson, S.A. and Kennaway, D. J. (2000). The ontogeny of induction of c-fos in the rat
641 SCN by a 5-HT(2A/2C) agonist. *Brain Res. Dev. Brain Res.* 121, 229–231

642 125. Ueda, S. *et al.* (1996) Alteration of serotonergic innervation in the suprachiasmatic
643 nucleus of the rat following removal of input fibers from retina and lateral geniculate
644 nucleus. *Neurosci. Lett.* 211, 97–100

645 126. Botchkina, G.I. and Morin, L. P. (1995) Specialized neuronal and glial contributions to
646 development of the hamster lateral geniculate complex and circadian visual system. *J.*
647 *Neurosci.* 15, 190–201

648 127. Ferguson, S.A. *et al.* (2000). Prenatal exposure to the dopamine agonist SKF-38393
649 disrupts the timing of the initial response of the suprachiasmatic nucleus to light. *Brain Res.*
650 858, 284–289

651 128. Buijs, R. M. *et al.* (1993) Projections of the suprachiasmatic nucleus to stress-related
652 areas in the rat hypothalamus: a light and electron microscopic study. *J. Comp. Neurol.* 335,
653 42–54

654 129. Buijs, F.N. *et al.* (2017) Suprachiasmatic Nucleus Interaction with the Arcuate Nucleus;
655 Essential for Organizing Physiological Rhythms. *eNeuro* 4, ENEURO.0028-17.2017

656 130. Acosta-Galvan, G. *et al.* (2011) Interaction between hypothalamic dorsomedial nucleus
657 and the suprachiasmatic nucleus determines intensity of food anticipatory behavior. *Proc.*
658 *Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 108, 5813–5818

659 131. Deurveilher, S. *et al.* (2002). Indirect projections from the suprachiasmatic nucleus to
660 the ventrolateral preoptic nucleus: a dual tract-tracing study in rat. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 16,
661 1195–1213

662 132. Deurveilher, S. and Semba, K. (2003) Indirect projections from the suprachiasmatic
663 nucleus to the median preoptic nucleus in rat. *Brain Res.* 987, 100–106

664 133. Ma, M.A. and Morrison, E.H. (2023) Neuroanatomy, Nucleus Suprachiasmatic in
665 *StatPearls*, Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing

666 134. Yao, Y. *et al.* (2023) Vasculature of the Suprachiasmatic Nucleus: Pathways for
667 Diffusible Output Signals. *J. Biol. Rhythms* 38, 571–585

668 135. Yao, Y. *et al.* (2021) Identification of the suprachiasmatic nucleus venous portal system
669 in the mammalian brain. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 5643

670 136. Mendez, N. *et al.* (2016) Gestational Chronodisruption Impairs Circadian Physiology in
671 Rat Male Offspring, Increasing the Risk of Chronic Disease. *Endocrinology* 157, 4654–4668

672 137. An, K. *et al.* (2020) A circadian rhythm-gated subcortical pathway for nighttime-light-
673 induced depressive-like behaviors in mice. *Nat. Neurosci.* 23, 869–880.

674 138. Kaur, S. *et al.* (2020) Circadian rhythm and its association with birth and infant
675 outcomes: research protocol of a prospective cohort study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, 20,
676 96

677

678 **Figure Legends**

679 **Figure 1: Multiscale organization of the circadian system.** The figure represents the three
680 levels of organization of the circadian system (molecular, tissue/circuit and systemic), and
681 examples of the three components: input, oscillator and output that are essential for receiving
682 temporal cues, integrating them and synchronizing downstream physiological processes.
683 Neurons are represented as yellow, green and blue circles and astrocytes as orange stars.
684 Abbreviations: Avp: vasopressin, BMAL1: brain and muscle aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear
685 translocator-like 1, CLOCK: circadian locomotor output cycles kaput, CRY1/2: Cryptochrome
686 1/2, GABA: gamma-aminobutyric acid, GCs: glucocorticoids, Glu: glutamate, MEL: melatonin,
687 Nms: Neuromedin S, OC: optic chiasm, Pacap: pituitary adenylate-cyclase-activating
688 polypeptide, PER1/2: Period 1/2, RHT: retinohypothalamic tract, SCN: suprachiasmatic nuclei,
689 T (°C): Temperature, Vip: Vasoactive intestinal peptide, 3V: third ventricle.

690

691 **Figure 2: Timeline of the master clock ontogeny in mice.** The figure represents the timeline
692 of the ontogeny of the hypothalamic SCN in mice during the perinatal period. The circuit
693 progresses from a collection of undifferentiated individual cells (grey circles), to a highly
694 differentiated, interconnected and synchronised multicellular network (neurons as green
695 circles and astrocytes as orange stars). In mice, around the time of neurogenesis (between
696 gestational day (GD) 10-15), SCN cells express clock genes with low amplitude oscillations and
697 low intercellular synchrony. By the time when the afferent retinal projections reach the SCN
698 and the eyes open (around postnatal day (PND) 12), the circuit express clock genes with high
699 amplitude oscillations and high intercellular synchrony. The maturation of the SCN as a circuit
700 occurs under the influence of maternal rhythmic hormonal signals during both the pre- and
701 post-natal periods (i.e.: signals that reach fetal/newborn tissues through placenta/breast
702 milk). Abbreviations: GD: Gestational day, Opn4: Melanopsin, PND: Postnatal day, RHT: retino
703 hypothalamic tract.

704

Maternal signals

